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The Possible demise of Ethiopia: Ethiopia's authoritarian to democratic transition and the challenges faced

Abstract

This study examines the factors contributing to the violent revolt against Dr. Abiy's legitimately elected administration, which sprang from the public movement in 2018. The analysis delves into the impact of US backing for the TPLF on exacerbating the conflict and investigates the progression of the situation into a prolonged internal battle between the governing authority and the deposed TPLF insurgents. It argues that the United States and its allies, as neocolonial actors, oppose the Ethiopian government's recent modifications to its domestic and foreign policies. These changes were met with resistance from the TPLF, a neocolonial regional organization. The TPLF's future political standing was threatened by Dr. Abiy's new international and internal policies, which were aimed at countering neocolonialism. Additionally, these policies endangered the geopolitical interests of the US in the region. This text contends that the modifications implemented by the current Ethiopian administration to previous policies were inspired by neocolonial entities and encountered opposition from neocolonial regional representatives, leading to the disturbance of Ethiopia's regional political and economic equilibrium. The study confirms the notion that the United States has exerted detrimental influence on Ethiopia's political system, which will have unfavorable consequences on Ethiopia's internal policies, particularly the ongoing shift from an authoritarian regime to a democratic one, as well as its foreign policy, particularly in relation to its dealings with neighboring nations. The study employs a synthesis of the process tracking methodology and case analysis to examine the research hypothesis.

Key words

2016 Ethiopian revolution, EPRDF/TPLF, Neocolonial actors, Neocolonial regional agent, from authoritarian to democratic, Dr. Abi Ahmed, Horn of Africa

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1. Introduction

In 2016, Ethiopians initiated a violent civil revolt against the autocratic rule of the EPRDF, a state that had held power for 27 years since 1991.¹ The EPDF-led regime, comprising multiple political parties representing different ethnicities, with the TPLF being the largest party from the Tigray region, was ultimately overthrown. On April 2, 2018, a new government, headed by Dr. Abiy, was democratically elected.² Nevertheless, despite the initial aspirations for peace, stability, and prosperity, along with the recognition that the region's negative image needed to be rectified,³ the argument has now shifted to the other viewpoint, and the country is teetering on the brink of collapse.⁴ Following the implementation of his new policies, a significant political dispute arose between Dr. Abiy Ahmed and the ousted TPLF party. This led to a direct conflict between the two factions on November 10, 2020, when the TPLF launched an attack on an Ethiopian army camp in the Tigray region, resulting in the death of the soldiers stationed there.⁵

Despite not being the first revolution, Ethiopia, the second-most populous country in Africa, has seen substantial political transformations since 1974. Commence with the Solomonic dynasty. Ethiopia was governed by a monarchy. The Solomonic Dynasty governed from the 13th century until the end of the 19th century, with its final monarch being Haile Selassie, who held power from 1930 to 1974. In 1974, Ethiopia transitioned from imperial rule for the first time. After the deposition of King Haile Selassie in 1974, Ethiopia was governed by a military regime under the leadership of Mengistu Haile Mariam from 1974 until 1991. The TPLF, which initiated the conflict in 1975 in collaboration with other ethnic factions established in 1989, enforced Mingiste's autocratic administration during the Gorilla War. The EPRDF is composed of various ethnic groups, namely the Oromo represented by the ODP (Oromo Democratic Party) constituting 34% of Ethiopia's population, ADP from the Amhara (Amhara Democratic Party) comprising 27%, the Tigray with 6% represented by the TPLF (Tigreya People's Liberated Front), and the southern Ethiopian tribes accounting for 10.5% represented by the SEPDM (Southern Ethiopia People's Democratic Movement).⁶

Consequently, Meles, the former prime minister and commander of the TPLF rebels, formed an authoritarian administration that lasted for 22 years. According to Wario Malicha, this was achieved through the massacre of 250,000 civilians and the displacement of one million people to

neighboring nations."⁷ Although the EPRDF initially established this government, it eventually transformed into a TPLF-dominated administration under the leadership of a TPLF leader, who held power from the day they took control in 1991 until his demise in 2012.⁸

Nevertheless, Ethiopia's economy has been seeing rapid growth, achieving a 6.3% expansion in FY2020/21.⁹ Prior to the uprising and the war between the Ethiopian federal government and the Tigrey-TPLF, the country's economy expanded rapidly, with real GDP growing at an average rate of 10.9% from 2000 to 2014. Ethiopia is the second-most populous country in Africa after Nigeria. Average yearly GDP per capita increase was 8.0 percent. As a result, in 2014, the nation's GDP dropped from second-poorest to eleventh-poorest globally.¹⁰

However, the TPLF had absolute authority over the administration of the country. Consequently, the entirety of the nation's authority has been consolidated within the control of a single ethnic group out of the country's 80. The TPLF has exploited the government as a façade to exert its authority, exemplified by its mistreatment of individuals from diverse ethnic backgrounds and its infringement upon their fundamental human rights. Furthermore, it has utilized the country's national jurisdiction and resources to cultivate the Tigray region, making it the most advanced and formidable region in terms of both development and military strength inside Ethiopia.¹¹

Individuals in Ethiopia, namely those belonging to ethnic groupings that did not align with the EPRDF and even those who were affiliated with the EPRDF, such as the Oromo, experienced the confiscation of their belongings, widespread instances of harsh torture and killings, arbitrary arrests without legal proceedings, and unexplained disappearances.¹² These occurrences became routine for the individuals, and they adapted to them. A significant exodus of individuals is occurring from the nation, although they are being denied political refuge by neighboring countries.¹³ The nation has evolved into a society where the occurrence of crimes and cruelty is unprecedented in comparison to the rest of the modern world in the twenty-first century. If the treatment of Ethiopian nationals under the TPLF-led government serves as an example, it suggests that the US and the West impose penalties and isolate other states.¹⁴

Ethiopia's foreign policy was increasingly displaying a more antagonistic disposition. An instance of this is its adversarial rapport with Eritrea and Somalia.¹⁵ It engaged in a violent conflict and suffered significant territorial losses against Eritrea,¹⁶ its neighboring country. Furthermore, it

engaged in military intervention in Somalia on two occasions, specifically in 2006 and 2009, perpetrating acts of genocide under the pretext of combating terrorism.¹⁷ Relations with Sudan were tense.¹⁸

Nevertheless, following the death of Prime Minister Meles, the authority and governance of the Tigrayan people started to disintegrate. The Oromo, the largest ethnic minority in the country, has initiated a civil revolt against the governing system, which has subsequently extended across the entire nation. The violent rebellion escalated beyond the control of Prime Minister Haile Mariam, who was perceived as a subordinate of the TPLF, acting in their favor.”¹⁹ Dr. Abiy Ahmed, the current Prime Minister of Ethiopia and a member of the country's largest ethnic group, the Oromo, was elected as the chairman of the EPRDF, the coalition that defeated Mengistu's dictatorial regime. The 2018 civilian uprising resulted in Abiy's election as Ethiopia's Prime Minister. This uprising arose from people's dissatisfaction with the government, implying that the government and those before it did not act in accordance with the will of the people. As a result, Dr. Abiy's rule has resulted from civil unrest.²⁰

Nevertheless, the Ethiopian EPRDF administration, formerly under the control of the TPLF for approximately thirty years, has been toppled by a civil revolt, resulting in Prime Minister Abiy Ahmed assuming power. Dr. Abiy introduced a policy change in Ethiopia and the surrounding region that was widely appreciated both domestically and internationally, especially by neighboring weak states.²¹ Nevertheless, he encountered substantial resistance from the ousted TPLF and the United States.²²

This study analyzes the political trajectory of Ethiopia's new prime minister, Dr. Abiy Ahmed, to comprehend the reasons behind the transformation of the country's democratic revolution, initially aimed at achieving human liberty, peace, prosperity, and the removal of the TPLF's authoritarian regime, into a state of political instability, civil war, and crises. The paper argues that the TPLF's uprising and Dr. Abiy's leadership should not be held responsible; instead, it suggests that the covert involvement of the US and the TPLF's revolution were both factors that instigated and aimed to oust Prime Minister Abiy. The study validates the premise that the involvement of the United States in Ethiopia's political system will have an adverse impact on Ethiopia's domestic politics and external relations, particularly with regard to its relationships with its neighbors.

It asserts that neocolonial actors' interference and neocolonial regional agents' rejection were factors in the present government of Ethiopia's decision to modify past policies. It highlights that Dr. Abiy's new anti-neocolonial domestic and foreign policies posed a danger to both the US's geopolitical interests in the region and the future political position of the TPLF. It argues that Ethiopia's present administration changed prior policies in response to neocolonial actors' interference and regional agents' opposition, shattering the political and economic stability of the region around Ethiopia.

2. Research methodology

This study uses a combination of the process tracking approach and case analysis to test the research hypothesis. This method is vital because it establishes a cause-and-effect relationship between concepts, such as the behaviors and expectations of the states. The political and neo-colonial crises in Ethiopia are regarded as contingent factors, while the policies of the US regarded as autonomous factors.

3. Abiy's accession to power and subsequent political changes

The Ethiopian revolution that toppled the TPLF regime and ushered in Dr. Abiy Ahmed was unexpected. At first, it appeared to be daybreak over the Horn of Africa.²³ Dr. Abiy Ahmed, whose country was "at the center of the Horn of Africa's political and economic state"²⁴ and democratic transition, has made significant progress that would tremendously benefit the region because he has taken swift and decisive action that has helped the region, particularly Ethiopia, Somalia, and Eritrea. This was widely agreed upon, as evidenced by his receipt of the Nobel Peace Prize. His success was aided by the fact that Abiy arrived at a time when the leaders of Somalia and Eritrea, Mohamed Abdilahi Farmajo and Assaisa Afwerki, respectively, were optimistic about Ethiopia's revolution and thus agreed to collaborate with him after the three leaders signed a tripartite agreement in Addis Abeba in June 2018.²⁵ As a result of their meeting and continued communication, the three leaders decided on regional integration.²⁶ While there is a notion suggesting that Dr. Abiy's efforts to enhance diplomatic ties with neighboring countries, especially Eritrea, were motivated by a desire to control the TPLF, it is logical to conclude that stopping hostilities and fostering amicable relations with them would contribute to the stability and prosperity of the region. This potential agreement may lead to the emergence of a new generation of charismatic leaders in the Horn of Africa region. It is noteworthy that the leaders of these three

countries, who have historically been enemies, have agreed for the first time to collaborate on the possibility of regional integration.

Abiy has initiated the process of returning to a state of normalcy in the relations between his country and Somalia and Eritrea. This has been achieved by resolving the border dispute between Ethiopia and Eritrea, which resulted in the deaths of over 135,000 Ethiopian soldiers and 19,000 Eritrean soldiers from 1998 to 2000.²⁷ Additionally, Abiy has successfully addressed the longstanding animosity between Ethiopia and Somalia, replacing it with a sense of brotherhood. Consequently, he terminated Ethiopia's detrimental engagement in Somalia and aided the central government of Somalia in reestablishing stability and reclaiming its autonomy. This is a significant and pivotal advancement for the region.²⁸ In Somalia, he counteracted the TPLF's practice of biased governance by closing down Ethiopian consulates in five regional administrations in Somalia, except for the Ethiopian embassy in Mogadishu. Additionally, he disarmed the Ethiopian Tigray soldiers present in Somalia.²⁹ and his diplomatic relations with Somalia have been limited to the central government, and he has removed the TPLF regime's direct diplomatic intervention relations with the leaders of Somalia's federal states' governments.³⁰

On the domestic front, however, he has accomplished great things that reflect the democratic path he has chosen, such as "freeing thousands of political prisoners, lifting press restrictions, welcoming back exiles and banned opposition parties, appointing women to positions in his cabinet, opening up the country's tightly-controlled economy to new investment..."³¹ Abiy's constructive domestic and foreign policy actions have had a positive and far-reaching impact on the Horn of Africa. His agreement with President Farmajo took effect nearly immediately, and Somalia has made significant political progress.³² As a result, the Somali government has taken steps to ensure that Somalia regains its dignity and position, as Ethiopia was the most significant impediment to establishing a functioning government in Somalia.³³

While some ideas in the region, specifically in Somalia and Ethiopia, express opposition towards Dr. Abiy's approach due to historical enmity and consequent lack of trust between the two nations, there exists a significant faction that ardently advocates for Dr. Abiy's regional policy. Based on their assertion, there exists a significant distinction between Abiy's administration and the TPLF's in Ethiopia, particularly in their approach towards the region. Given that Somalis reside on both sides of the border and maintain deep familial connections, regular travel between Somalia and

Ethiopia is consistently required. However, the ease of travel between Somalia and Ethiopia (including Somalia, Somaliland, and Ethiopia) has significantly improved compared to the past, which is advantageous for the Somali individuals residing in both nations. Somalis can now conveniently depart from Hargeisa and other urban centers to journey to Addis Ababa, whereas the Ethiopian government under TPLF rule had previously imposed obstacles to hinder their movement.

Under the oppressive rule of the TPLF regime, numerous individuals who journeyed to Ethiopia experienced enforced disappearances, unjust imprisonment leading to lifelong incarceration, and brutal acts of torture and death. The Somalis who are not under the control of the Ethiopian government, the Somali state within Ethiopia that has some self-governance, and other Ethiopians were extremely happy about the political changes and reforms in Ethiopia. They believed that the region was now secure since the oppressive colonial rule of the TPLF had been overthrown. Hence, this suggests that Ethiopians have successfully overcome the oppressive rule of the TPLF dictatorship. As stated by Abbera, ""Ethiopia had a brutal dictatorial regime that exiled, imprisoned, tortured, and killed its political opponents, as well as journalists, professors, civil society leaders, and demonstrators."34

3.1. The complications of the transition from authoritarianism to democracy

Dr. Abiy introduced distinct foreign and domestic policies, diverging from previous authoritarian governments, which were suitable for his country and surrounding nations. However, once Ethiopia became entangled in a complex and difficult political position, the circumstances rapidly worsened. On November 10, 2020, a civil war broke out between the TPLF rebels, who formerly governed the Tigrean state government in Ethiopia, and Dr. Abiy Ahmed's federal administration. The war began when the TPLF launched an attack on the Ethiopian Northern Command bases in Tigray, resulting in their destruction. Prime Minister Abiy asserts that he is compelled to respond to the TPLF's actions with the use of force.³⁵

In addition, despite Dr. Abiy's several efforts to engage in dialogue with the TPLF before to the start of the war, the TPLF refused due to resentment. Alternatively, they initiated a campaign with the intention of subverting the central authority. Nevertheless, the US and Western governments made no effort to convince the TPLF to cease their attacks on Abiy's government or to facilitate

any form of conflict resolution. In contrast, the Western governments shifted their criticism towards Dr. Abiy following his government's victory over the TPLF in response to the TPLF's overt aggression. They also announced their intention to exert economic and diplomatic pressure, with the ultimate goal of compelling Dr. Abiy to withdraw his troops and allies from the Tigrean region they had occupied during the conflict, as a result of Western sanctions and diplomatic pressure. The TPLF perceived this as a favorable circumstance, whilst the federal government regarded it as a hindrance. The TPLF, under the leadership of Tigreans, responded by crossing the border and successfully capturing large portions of the Amhara and Anfar regions.³⁶

The apprehension regarding the government's ability to quell the TPLF has escalated significantly. Given that the TPLF has maintained complete governance over the past 27 years, consolidating all power within one of the 80 ethnic groups, and has utilized natural resources and authority to transform Ethiopia's Tigray region into the most advanced and militarily formidable area in the nation, there is apprehension regarding the government's ability to overcome the TPLF. The success of their conflict against the government seems unlikely without the backing of the local, ethnic, and external groups. This exemplifies the present condition of the war: they successfully gained dominance over the fight, eliminated a substantial amount of government forces, apprehended tens of thousands of soldiers, and progressed towards the capital with the intention of conquering it.

However, despite its interaction with the TPLF, the US has done little to stop the war. Instead, it has concentrated its efforts on delivering humanitarian aid to the Tigrean region. According to how the US is responding to Ethiopia's federal government's fight against the TPLF by claiming to be backing Tigray as a humanitarian concern, they lied.³⁷ People in Ethiopia, including those who ardently supported and believed that the US always fought for the promotion of democracy, realized that by aiding the TPLF's effort to topple Prime Minister Dr. Abiy Ahmed and his administration, the US was worsening rather than improving the situation for democracy in Ethiopia. even while some assert that the government is to blame Protests were held all around Ethiopia, but especially in Addis Ababa and other significant cities.³⁸ Similar demonstrations also took place in other nations, including the US and Canada.³⁹ Demonstrations both inside and outside of Ethiopia targeted the US's support of the TPLF.⁴⁰

On September 17, 2021, US President Biden imposed sanctions on some government officials, accusing Ethiopia of endangering US national security. On May 24, of that year, Biden imposed yet another travel ban on other government officials based on alleged human rights violations. On February 27, Antony Blinken ordered the withdrawal of Eritrean and Amhara Maletia troops assisting federal government troops in the Tigray region. For security reasons, the United States has halted \$272 million in aid to Ethiopia. It stopped donating the \$923 million in aid to the Ethiopian government that it used to do every year. All of this is being done to bring Dr. Abiy's government down.⁴¹

3.2. Reasons Behind the Ethiopian Political Crisis and Civil War

Owing to the United States' intervention and Ethiopia's colonial legacy, the democratic uprising in Ethiopia, aimed at achieving peace, prosperity, and the removal of the TPLF government, has deteriorated into a state of political instability, civil conflict, and political emergencies. There are two factors contributing to Ethiopia's present state and the deviation of the Ethiopian revolution from its intended objectives. This has led to undesirable and unexpected consequences such as a political crisis, civil war, and national devastation, with the involvement of the United States. There are two primary factors contributing to Ethiopia's current predicament: "Foreign (US) intervention," (can be described as the involvement of the United States in the affairs of another country),⁴² According to Yohannes Woldemariam and Nic Cheeseman, Dr. Abiy developed a new national policy with the goal of creating a genuinely democratic Ethiopia that is not influenced by neocolonialism and does not prioritize the interests of the United States and its allies. The second element involves a power struggle between Dr. Abiy's administration and the TPLF, which is being exacerbated by the United States. This approach also resulted in a power struggle between Prime Minister Dr. Abiy, who was elected through a democratic process, and the administration led by the Tigrean faction that was ousted from office.⁴³ Consequently, a conflict for control arose between the TPLF and Ethiopia's prime minister, Dr. Abiy, immediately after he took office subsequent to the 2016 revolution.⁴⁴

3.2.1. Power struggle between the Prime Minister Dr. Abiy and the TPLF

There exists a sense of ethnic group dominance in Ethiopia. The Amhara and Tigrayan ethnic groups of Abyssinia hold a belief of superiority over other ethnic groups, asserting that only their

religion and culture should be observed inside the nation. Additionally, they possess a belief that they own authority and that all others should acquiesce to their dominance. The two ethnic groups have a long history of power conflicts among themselves. It signifies that when either the Tigre or Amhara ethnic group assumes power in the nation, it subjugates the remaining ethnicities through colonization.⁴⁵

As a result, because Dr. Abiy is of Oromo descent, the TPLF found it impossible to acknowledge him as Ethiopia's Prime Minister. Nevertheless, as they were unable to confront him directly, they endeavored to negotiate with him privately, similar to their approach with Hailemariam Desalegn,⁴⁶ in order to retain their authority. However, their efforts were unsuccessful because Abiy firmly insisted on maintaining the autonomy of his position.⁴⁷ He declined to heed the TPLF leaders, who advocated for the preservation of the incumbent dictatorship. The establishment of the PP and the departure of the EPRDF signify,⁴⁸ that the TPLF has experienced a significant decline in its power and influence.⁴⁹ according to BBC News.

He promptly started making crucial decisions that were essential for his survival and to uphold his authority in the position he attained during Ethiopia's 2016 revolution. The TPLF perceived that Dr. Abiy's swift actions had the potential to dismantle their economic and political dominance that they had built up over the past 27 years. They realized that they had no control over the country, which was now independently implementing domestic and foreign policies without their influence.⁵⁰ Furthermore, they acknowledged that the country could be held responsible for its violent actions against other ethnic groups, such as the Oromo, who had gained power.⁵¹ Consequently, they initiated efforts to restore control.⁵²

Abiy executed precisely the actions that instilled dread in them, resulting in a transformation of both foreign and domestic policy. He resolved the Ethiopia-Eritrea border dispute, which resulted in a minimum of 200,000 fatalities from 1998 to 2000, along with the aggressive Ethiopian involvement in Somalia. Consequently, the TPLF has been unable to embrace Abiy's proposal to change Ethiopia's hostile connection with the region into a friendly one, which would lead to peace, stability, cooperation, integration, and progress among the communities in the area. The prospective modifications in Abiy's foreign policy have impacted the TPLF's.⁵³

They perceived Abiy's declaration of apprehending TPLF regime individuals, such as Ethiopia's Somali state president, Abdi Iley, and the commander of Ethiopian forces in Somalia, General Gabre Heard, for offenses like crimes against humanity and misuse of power, among other transgressions, as a form of intimidation. They also interpreted the announcement of detaining TPLF regime members as a move that involved releasing a significant number of political prisoners, easing restrictions on the press, welcoming back exiles, and prohibiting opposition."⁵⁴ Abiy Ahmed has accomplished significant feats that will considerably help the area, and these policies, along with numerous others, have contributed to the region's rapid development. Nevertheless, from the perspective of Western governments observers and as Mosley articulates on behalf of the TPLF, the situation is misinterpreted to be a concerted campaign against the Tigrean people.⁵⁵

Not only was the TPF's political dominance in Ethiopia under threat from Abiy's democratic system, but the 27-year-old political regime's economic hegemony was also under risk. Because this democratic system was established through popular uprising rather than a coup, the Abiy government became a pure democracy and far from the TPLF's. As a result, garnering widespread public support, Abiy's government and its associated political and economic policies eliminated the TPLF's usual corruption, ability to control the country's resources, strong ties to the military, intelligence, and security, and what was seen as illegal trade through EFFORT, Ethiopia's largest business, with a capital value of US \$30 billion and employing 47,000 Tigreans. At one point, the TPLF found itself isolated and deprived of its ability to facilitate the issuance of loans from state banks, obtain foreign exchange from the National Bank of Ethiopia, and take "various assets from government institutions."⁵⁶

As a result, they decided to flee to Maqale, their region's capital, to regroup and overthrow Abiy's democratic government, which had been brought about by the uprising, by utilizing western-biased media outlets. One of the most heinous and mysterious actions it committed was to attack Ethiopian forces stationed in their region, which it ruled for 27 years, who remained to protect the Tigrayan region from Eritrea following the border war between the two countries.⁵⁷

Indeed, as they had anticipated, it undoubtedly turned out to be a menacing warning. The TPLF, a totalitarian dictatorship, viewed the new democratic system as a threat due to its origins in a civilian uprising. The TPLF had forcefully controlled the country for the previous 27 years and

had been responsible for committing numerous crimes against humanity.⁵⁸ Typically, when a revolt removes a dictatorial regime, the ousted officials are subject to prosecution. Indeed, Abiy's actions provide as a clear demonstration of what precisely occurred. Consequently, they have chosen to establish a local insurgent group to counteract the governing body.⁵⁹

Evidently, the TPLF was resistant to any kind of governance in Ethiopia that deviated from its own established model. Put simply, their objective was to establish an authoritarian government to govern the nation and maintain unfavorable and antagonistic relationships with neighboring countries due to their apprehension of facing legal consequences for their wrongdoing. Nevertheless, it was revealed that Abiy was a resolute leader dedicated to governing in accordance with his own ideology and democratic principles, regardless of the TPLF's formidable power and control acquired over the course of their 27-year rule over many Ethiopian institutions. Upon discovering that the country was deviating from the TPLF's anticipated trajectory, they hastily confronted Abiy. Consequently, Abiy has faced multiple instances of coups and killings.⁶⁰

The TPLF swiftly rebelled against the Abiy leadership, aiming to undermine its stability. The TPLF, being a capable and influential administration, functioned almost as an autonomous entity within a larger government that relied on Western governments support. The TPLF implemented two strategic actions throughout its rule to ensure the long-term stability of its territory and uphold its power inside the nation. Throughout their reign, they systematically advanced their federal state government (regional government) in terms of economy, society, military, and administration. Additionally, they expanded their international alliances⁶¹ by using the natural and human resources of other Ethiopian ethnic groups. Hence, they regarded the act of combatting and toppling Abiy's administration as a straightforward affair.⁶²

3.2.2. US intervention in the path of Ethiopia's bloody revolution for democracy

One further factor that led to Ethiopia's involvement in political turmoil and civil war, instead of the anticipated progress, was the interference of the US and its western allies through neocolonial means, utilizing their media and the overthrown TPLF administration.⁶³ Western governments appear to be unaware of the events that took place in Ethiopia during the TPLF's authoritarian rule, and they demonstrate a lack of concern.⁶⁴ Due to the primacy and significance of their own interests in the region, they are against and express disapproval towards policies that are

detrimental to their interests. Consequently, they do not endorse Ethiopia's beneficial political transition, which would be advantageous for both the nation and the region.⁶⁵ However, the Western governments are providing significant support to the TPLF's attempt to regain control, aiming to disrupt the democratic Abiy administration that came into office after a revolution in 2016. The West's hypocrisy is evident in their conflicting acts.⁶⁶ Fourth The United States is renowned for asserting its diligent efforts in promoting and enhancing democracy globally. However, they are perceived as endorsing autocratic regimes and opposing democratic ones. Their method and involvement in Ethiopia's political turmoil serve as a prominent illustration.⁶⁷

Ethiopians believe that the United States backs the TPLF with the intention of protecting its own interests in Ethiopia and the surrounding area, rather than prioritizing the interests of Ethiopia and the region as a whole, in contrast to the TPLF insurgents. Consequently, the TPLF's objective is to prevent Ethiopia from achieving independence from the US,⁶⁸ while simultaneously desiring a democratic Ethiopia but with the intention of reinstating a dictatorship.⁶⁹ This detrimental intervention seeks to undermine the entire region.⁷⁰ Given that Ethiopia is the central point of the Horn of Africa, it is evident that the political transformations resulting from the country's revolution might potentially benefit the area, whereas the present disorder and unrest will likely have an adverse effect. As Aly states, the well-being of Ethiopia is beneficial for the entire area, and conversely, what benefits the region is also advantageous for Ethiopia."⁷¹

This elucidates the reason behind the United States' consistent unwillingness to accept governments, regardless of their democratic nature, that were unable to further its own interests. The Horn nations will possess full state sovereignty and authority if they effectively and democratically align themselves. Hence, the United States' involvement in the region must incur significant expenses, otherwise its influence will diminish. This is the reason why the United States is against Abiy's legitimately elected government. Abiy appears to be a leader who advocates for the national interests of Ethiopia and the Horn of Africa. However, they are unable to pursue their own goals due to the presence of the TPLF, which is seen as a symbol of neo-colonialism in the Horn of Africa.⁷²

Historically, the United States has been unwilling to embrace a democracy that conflicts with its own interests. Here are two instances of the United States' foreign policy initiatives in respect to two emerging democracies on the global stage.

3.2.3. Mohamed Morsi, first Egyptian democratically president, elected Iran's 35th PM, Mohamed Mossadegh, and Chile's 28th President, Salvador Allende

Examine the political figures of Mohamed Mossadegh from Iran and Salvador Allende from Chile. "I don't see why we need to stand by and watch a country go communist because of the irresponsibility of its own people." —Henry Kissinger, June 27, 1970.⁷³ This is a statement Kissinger made when he was talking about the issue of Allende.

Upon examining historical records, it becomes evident that the United States has been reluctant to embrace a democracy that conflicts with its own interests. Examine the 35th Prime Minister of Iran, Mohamed Mossadegh, and the 28th President of Chile, Salvador Allende. The United States became Salvador Allende's primary opponent when he campaigned for the presidency of the Republic of Chile in 1970. The sole reason for this was that, despite his democratic election, Allende's adherence to Marxism led him to nationalize key businesses, including as copper mining, within his own nation. Consequently, the United States acknowledged Chile as a prospective menace to the area. Consequently, it was imperative to overthrow Allende. The United States has initiated a covert operation utilizing the Central Intelligence Agency (CIA) with the objective of undermining the stability of the Allende government. Their victory was intended to provoke the Chilean populace into resisting the president and uniting in support of his adversaries. The propaganda effort targeting Allende alone incurred a cost of \$20 million, with one of its primary objectives being to caution parents about the imminent risk of their children adopting Marxist ideologies. The second objective aimed to undermine the stability of the Chilean economy, while the third objective involved allocating \$10 million to carry out the assassination of both Allende and the commander of the national force, General René Schneider. General Schneider was promptly slain, succeeding Augusto Pinochet, who orchestrated the coup. The democratically elected president was slain on November 11, 1973, but there was a prevalent belief that he had taken his own life.⁷⁴

Subsequent to the coup, the military dictatorship that assumed control perpetrated infringements upon human rights. A total of 3,000 individuals lost their lives, excluding those who remain unaccounted for. Tens of thousands of individuals were subjected to torture. Instances of sexual assault, including acts committed by canines specifically trained for this purpose, were reported.

Notwithstanding the military's coup against the democratic government and the subsequent regime's heinous acts, the US government promptly provided financial and political support to them.⁷⁵

Mohamed Mossadegh, the 35th Prime Minister and the first democratically elected leader, became a target of the United Kingdom and the United States due to his decision to nationalize his country's oil business. Following Mossadegh's opposition to the unequal distribution of Iran's oil income, where Iran received a mere 16 percent and Britain claimed the rest 84 percent, the decision was made to nationalize the oil. Britain declined to alter this stance when Mohamed Mossadegh attempted to do so. Consequently, Mossadegh opted to nationalize the production of oil. This resulted in a significant division between the two nations. Consequently, Mohamed Mossadegh developed a hostile view towards Britain and cut off all connections with the country.⁷⁶

Mohamed Mursi serves as a prime example of this. In 2013, a coup occurred with the aim of deposing the president of Egypt who had been elected democratically in 2012. Just like the Ethiopian revolution in 2016 led to the election of Dr. Abiy as Ethiopia's prime minister in 2018, the Egyptian revolution in 2011 toppled Hosni Mubarak's oppressive regime. The problem resulted in significant loss of life, but in 2012, the Egyptian people successfully elected Mohamed Morsi as their president through a democratic process. In relation to this issue, the US government chose not to comment and implicitly supported the coup, while concurrently providing military support to the Syrian rebels in their endeavor to overthrow Bashar from his position.⁷⁷

The United States is committed to overthrowing Dr. Abiy's lawful, democratic, and historically unprecedented government, which emerged after a violent civil revolt. This pertains to the United States' policy regarding Ethiopia, the Horn of Africa region, and the entire continent. The United States and Ethiopia maintain bilateral, regional, and continental relationships. US interests are headquartered in Ethiopia, serving as both the regional and continental hub. The United States utilizes this country as a means to safeguard and promote its interests in the Horn of Africa region. This region holds significance for the US due to its proximity to the oil-rich Middle East, as well as its strategic location along the Indian Ocean oil route and the Red Sea passage to the Mediterranean Sea.

Despite the US administration's inclination to oust Abiy and the significant deterioration of their relationship, Dr. Abiy has agreed to participate in the US-African leaders' conference in the US.

The situation is surprising for those who are acquainted with the acrimonious rapport between the two countries, specifically Dr. Abiy and the United States. Although it may seem to undermine the US government's desire to have Dr. Abiy removed from office, the invitation was actually received by the president of Ethiopia, Sahle-Work Zewde, who then passed it on to Dr. Abiy. The US allowed the invitees to forward the invitation to anyone they desired.⁷⁸

Consequently, the United States diligently monitors any alterations that take place in that nation. According to a declassified document from the Department of State, specifically the PA/HO department, in 1976, the United States expressed significant concern regarding the shift in the Ethiopian government. This issue arose when Mengiste, who had cut Ethiopia's diplomatic relations with the US, came to power after the fall of King Haile Selassie, who had been a close ally of the United States. During that period, the United States relinquished authority over its military installation in Kagnew, which served as a radio station, as well as its ability to utilize ports and airfields in Asmara.⁷⁹

In 1903, three years after the establishment of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs by Emperor Menelik II, diplomatic ties were established between the United States and Ethiopia. The bond between the United States and Hailes Elessie was particularly robust during his rule, spanning from 1931 to 1974, as he maintained a close friendship with the United States. The relationship deteriorated during the Derge military administration's control of the nation from 1976 until 1991. However, the United States maintained apprehension of Ethiopia's adversarial relationships with Derge until 1991, when the EPRDF, led by the TPLF, took control. Due to the emergence of terrorist groups such as Al-Qaida and pirates, Ethiopia's importance to the United States has grown as security worries have heightened.⁸⁰

Conclusion

The Ethiopian population, having experienced prolonged hardship under a monarchy and subsequent dictatorship, saw positive outcomes under the leadership of Dr. Abiy's government. This government emerged as a response to the oppressive rule of the TPLF, which was overthrown through a violent war for liberation. Additionally, it is the entity that fosters stability and tranquility in the region. However, the TPLF is currently engaged in a struggle to reclaim control, encountering strong resistance, and receiving assistance from the United States.⁸¹

The government led by Dr. Abiy has achieved notable advancements within the country, which demonstrate its commitment to the democratic trajectory it has embraced. Illustrative instances encompass "designating females to positions within his cabinet, extending invitations to exiles and proscribed opposition parties, releasing numerous political detainees, abolishing press constraints, and liberalizing the nation's tightly regulated economy to fresh investments..."⁸²

Abiy launched the transformation of Ethiopia's hostile relationship with the area into a friendly one, leading to peace, stability, cooperation, integration, and development among the societies in the region.⁸³ The Horn of Africa has experienced significant and profound advantages as a result of Abiy's effective and extensive domestic and foreign policy endeavors. The agreement between him and President Farmajo was implemented immediately, resulting in significant political progress in Somalia. Previously, Ethiopia posed a major hindrance to the establishment of a functional government in Somalia. Consequently, the Somali government has taken measures to restore Somalia's dignity and status.⁸⁴ Ethiopia posed a significant barrier to Somalia's efforts to build an effective government. Consequently, the Somali government has implemented measures to guarantee the restoration of Somalia's honor and position.⁸⁵

Abiy has initiated the restoration of normalcy in Ethiopia's relations with Somalia and Eritrea by resolving the border dispute that caused the deaths of a significant number of soldiers from both countries.⁸⁶ This has also put an end to the longstanding hostility between Ethiopia and Somalia, replacing it with a sense of brotherhood.⁸⁷ He halted Ethiopia's calamitous involvement in Somalia and aided in the restoration of law and order and the recovery of its sovereignty by the country's central authority.⁸⁸

As previously mentioned, Dr. Abiy's rational and praiseworthy activities have the potential to contribute to the ongoing political reform that the country has been experiencing over the past five decades. His decisions regarding internal and foreign matters have enhanced political stability and freedom in Ethiopia as well as the surrounding nations. He implemented several significant and essential enhancements, such as ensuring the protection of fundamental human rights like freedom of the press and speech, and fostering amicable relations among different regions to prevent potential conflicts that could have led to numerous casualties, possibly in the range of thousands or even hundreds of thousands.

This indicates that Abiy took a substantial step towards enhancing the unfavorable perception of the Horn of Africa. Therefore, the citizens of Ethiopia and the neighboring region expected that this revolution would yield positive results,⁸⁹ and deemed it deserving of support, especially from the United States of America, which prides itself on being at the forefront of promoting democracy and safeguarding human rights. However, subsequent events took a negative turn, leading to a formidable opposition emerging against both the USA and the TPLF. This resistance escalated into a violent civil war, causing political instability and casting doubt on the nation's future, potentially leading to its complete collapse.⁹⁰ The current situation might be attributed to American interference, aimed at reinstating the TPLF's power after its removal, in order to protect its own interests in Ethiopia and the neighboring region.⁹¹ The United States of America adopted this measure upon seeing that Dr. Abiy's ruling might impede their ability to pursue their own objectives in the region.⁹²

Nevertheless, it is abundantly clear that if the TPLF regains control, Ethiopia will find itself in a precarious state, characterized by unpredictability and the potential establishment of a dictatorship. Consequently, the region will witness a resurgence of antagonistic relations between Ethiopia and the neighboring countries, particularly Somalia and Eritrea. This is due to the comparison between the pre-uprising conditions in the country and the region, and the current state of a democratic administration that has emerged as a result of civil upheaval.

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